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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Congenital müllerian anomalies may also be asymptomatic, so their frequency cannot be clearly expressed. The prevalence has been reported as 5.5% - 8%. This rate was found to increase in patients with a history of pregnancy loss and/or infertility (24.5%). We aimed to present a case of unicorn uterus, a müllerian anomaly, who reached term in good health and was incidentally diagnosed during cesarean section.

Case Presentation: A 33-year-old G1P0 patient had no problem in screening tests and detailed ultrasonography during pregnancy follow-up. The pregnancy was continued with strict ultrasonography and Doppler follow-up until 38 weeks, but due to the onset of contractions and breech presentation of the fetus, she was delivered by cesarean section. During cesarean section, it was observed that the uterus was unicorn. A rudimentary horn and attached right ovary and tuba were observed on the right. The patient was informed after the operation and told that she should come for follow-up.

Discussion: Congenital uterine anomalies include septate, bicornuate, didelphys and unicornuate uterus and are caused by abnormal formation, fusion or resorption of the müllerian ducts. In the unicornuate uterus, one cavity is usually smaller than a normal uterus and has a fallopian tube, ovary, and cervix, while the failed müllerian duct has various configurations. The affected müllerian duct may not develop at all, or it may develop only partially as either a rudimentary horn on the uterus or an anlage (a cluster of embryonic cells). This horn (or anlage) may or may not communicate with the uterus. MRI can be useful to more reliably assess for the presence of a rudimentary horn with or without functional endometrium and an ectopic ovary. Most rudimentary horns are asymptomatic. If a rudimentary horn is obstructed (without communication to the other uterus or cervix), the patient may develop cyclic or chronic abdominopelvic pain. An obstructed or rudimentary uterine horn is also associated with uterine rupture. Patients with unicornuate uteri are generally not candidates for reconstructive procedures to improve pregnancy outcomes.

Conclusion: In our case, there was no pre-pregnancy symptom due to rudimentary horn, and it was detected incidentally during caesarean section. Therefore, the preliminary diagnosis of our case may be noncommunicating rudimentary horn without functional endometrium. Uterine anomalies may cause fertility-related and obstetric problems or may be detected incidentally without any symptoms as in our case. Therefore, correct identification and appropriate management of uterine anomalies are important.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Müllerian anomaly, unicorn uterus, caesarean section, rudimentary horn

INTRODUCTION

Congenital müllerian anomalies may also be asymptomatic, so their frequency cannot be clearly expressed. The prevalence has been reported as 5.5% - 8% (Chan et al., 2011). This rate was found to increase in patients with a history of pregnancy loss and/or infertility (24.5%). Congenital müllerian anomalies may cause pelvic pain, abnormal uterine bleeding, abortion, preterm labor, anomalies of presentation and intrauterine growth retardation. We aimed to present a case of unicorn uterus, a müllerian anomaly, who reached term in good health and was incidentally diagnosed during cesarean section.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 33-year-old G1P0 patient had no problem in screening tests and detailed ultrasonography during pregnancy follow-up. Until the 30th week of gestation, the fetus was developing in accordance with its week of gestation, but after the 30th week, the fetus started to have small measurements compared to its week of gestation. The pregnancy was continued with strict ultrasonography and Doppler follow-up until 38 weeks, but due to the onset of contractions and breech presentation of the fetus, she was delivered by cesarean section as a small gestational age (SGA) baby. During cesarean section, it was observed that the uterus was unicorn. A rudimentary horn and attached right ovary and tuba were observed on the right (Figure 1). The patient was informed after the operation and told that she should come for follow-up. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient.

Figure 1

Congenital uterine anomalies include septate, bicornuate, didelphis and unicornuate uterus and are caused by abnormal formation, fusion or resorption of the müllerian ducts. Trans vaginal USG, HSG, 3D-USG and MRI can be used in the diagnosis of müllerian anomalies (Pellerito, McCarthy, Doyle, Glickman, & DeCherney, 1992). Combined laparoscopy/hysteroscopy may be required for definitive diagnosis and treatment of the detected anomaly is also possible. Since reproductive outcomes vary according to the type of anomaly, it is important to identify the anomaly. In the unicornuate uterus, one cavity is usually smaller than a normal uterus and has a fallopian tube, ovary, and cervix, while the failed müllerian duct has various configurations. The affected müllerian duct may not develop at all, or it may develop only partially as either a rudimentary horn on the uterus or an anlage (a cluster of embryonic cells). This horn (or anlage) may or may not communicate with the uterus. The diagnosis is typically based on imaging findings of a uterus deviated to one side of the pelvis with an inner contour demonstrating a tubular rather than triangular configuration; 3D-reconstructed images are particularly helpful. MRI can be useful to more reliably assess for the presence of a rudimentary horn with or without functional endometrium and an ectopic ovary. Most rudimentary horns are asymptomatic. Some contain functional, but not necessarily normal, endometrium that is shed cyclically (Jayasinghe, Rane, Stalewski, & Grover, 2005). If a rudimentary horn is obstructed (without communication to the other uterus or cervix), the patient may develop cyclic or chronic abdominopelvic pain. Patients with a unicornuate uterus are also at higher risk for endometriosis. A literature review of pregnancy outcomes in patients with unicornuate uteri reported the following adverse pregnancy outcomes: first-trimester pregnancy loss (24.3 percent), preterm birth (20.1 percent), second-trimester pregnancy loss (9.7 percent), fetal demise (3.8 percent), ectopic pregnancy (2.7 percent); over half (51.5 percent) of patients experienced a live birth (Jayasinghe et al., 2005; Reichman, Laufer, & Robinson, 2009). An obstructed or rudimentary uterine horn is also associated with uterine rupture and/or placental attachment abnormalities (eg, accreta, increta, percreta)

(Contreras, Rothenberg, Kominiarek, & Raff, 2008; Daskalakis, Pilalis, Lykeridou, & Antsaklis, 2002; Henriët et al., 2008; Jayasinghe et al., 2005). A study of 328 pregnancies in obstructed horns found that only 1 percent of such pregnancies were alive at term, and 89 percent of the horns ruptured (O'Leary & O'Leary, 1963). Both spontaneous rupture and rupture during labor or induction have been reported. Thus, pregnancies in an obstructed horn should be terminated. Unicornuate uterus can also be associated with an ectopic ovary (which is of clinical importance in patients undergoing ovulation induction or who develop ovarian neoplasms) (Dabirashrafi, Mohammad, & Moghadami-Tabrizi, 1994; Ombelet, Verswijvel, & de Jonge, 2003), and a particularly high incidence (40 percent) of renal abnormalities (Fedele, Bianchi, Agnoli, Tozzi, & Vignali, 1996). Patients with unicornuate uteri are generally not candidates for reconstructive procedures to improve pregnancy outcomes (Acién, Acién, & Sánchez-Ferrer, 2004). However, as a rudimentary horn with functioning endometrium can result in cyclic or chronic abdominopelvic pain or harbor an ectopic pregnancy, noncommunicating rudimentary horns with endometrium are sometimes surgically removed. In our case, there was no pre-pregnancy symptom due to rudimentary horn and it was detected incidentally during caesarean section. Therefore, the preliminary diagnosis of our case may be noncommunicating rudimentary horn without functional endometrium. However, MRI was recommended for definitive diagnosis and to investigate whether there was an accompanying renal anomaly. The complications that rudimentary horns may cause in the future were explained to the patient and excision was offered as an option, but the patient refused. In retrospective evaluation, it was thought that SGA and breech presentation of the fetus may have been due to unicorn uterus.

DISCUSSION

Congenital uterine anomalies include septate, bicornuate, didelphis and unicornuate uterus and are caused by abnormal formation, fusion or resorption of the müllerian ducts. Trans vaginal USG, HSG, 3D-USG and MRI can be used in the diagnosis of müllerian anomalies (Pellerito, McCarthy, Doyle, Glickman, & DeCherney, 1992). Combined laparoscopy/hysteroscopy may be required for definitive diagnosis and treatment of the detected anomaly is also possible. Since reproductive outcomes vary according to the type of anomaly, it is important to identify the anomaly. In the unicornuate uterus, one cavity is usually smaller than a normal uterus and has a fallopian tube, ovary, and cervix, while the failed müllerian duct has various configurations. The affected müllerian duct may not develop at all, or it may develop only partially as either a rudimentary horn on the uterus or an anlage (a cluster of embryonic cells). This horn (or anlage) may or may not communicate with the uterus. The diagnosis is typically based on imaging findings of a uterus deviated to one side of the pelvis with an inner contour demonstrating a tubular rather than triangular configuration; 3D-reconstructed images are particularly helpful. MRI can be useful to more reliably assess for the presence of a rudimentary horn with or without functional endometrium and an ectopic ovary. Most rudimentary horns are asymptomatic. Some contain functional, but not necessarily normal, endometrium that is shed cyclically (Jayasinghe, Rane, Stalewski, & Grover, 2005). If a rudimentary horn is obstructed (without communication to the other uterus or cervix), the patient may develop cyclic or chronic abdominopelvic pain. Patients with a unicornuate uterus are also at higher risk for endometriosis. A literature review of pregnancy outcomes in patients with unicornuate uteri reported the following adverse pregnancy outcomes: first-trimester pregnancy loss (24.3 percent), preterm birth (20.1 percent), second-trimester pregnancy loss (9.7 percent), fetal demise (3.8 percent), ectopic pregnancy (2.7 percent); over half (51.5 percent) of patients experienced a live birth (Jayasinghe et al., 2005; Reichman, Laufer, & Robinson, 2009). An obstructed or rudimentary uterine horn is also associated with uterine rupture and/or placental attachment abnormalities (eg, accreta, increta, percreta) (Contreras, Rothenberg, Kominiarek, & Raff, 2008; Daskalakis, Pilalis, Lykeridou, & Antsaklis, 2002; Henriët et al., 2008; Jayasinghe et al., 2005). A study of 328 pregnancies in obstructed horns found that only 1 percent of such pregnancies were alive at term, and 89 percent of the horns ruptured (O'Leary & O'Leary, 1963). Both spontaneous rupture and rupture during labor or induction have been reported. Thus, pregnancies in an obstructed horn should be terminated. Unicornuate uterus can also be associated with an ectopic ovary (which is of clinical importance in patients undergoing ovulation induction or who develop ovarian neoplasms) (Dabirashrafi, Mohammad, & Moghadami-Tabrizi, 1994; Ombelet, Verswijvel, & de Jonge, 2003), and a particularly high incidence (40 percent) of renal abnormalities (Fedele, Bianchi, Agnoli, Tozzi, & Vignali, 1996). Patients with unicornuate uteri are generally not candidates for reconstructive procedures to improve pregnancy outcomes (Acién, Acién, & Sánchez-Ferrer, 2004). However, as a rudimentary horn

with functioning endometrium can result in cyclic or chronic abdominopelvic pain or harbor an ectopic pregnancy, noncommunicating rudimentary horns with endometrium are sometimes surgically removed. Uterine anomalies may cause fertility-related and obstetric problems or may be detected incidentally without any symptoms as in our case. Therefore, correct identification and appropriate management of uterine anomalies are important.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this case.

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